

Characters of male sterile lines evaluated in 1983-86 at CLRRI, Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Male sterile (A)	Maintainer (B)	Maturity (d)	Height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicle exertion	Spikelet sterility (%)	Seed setting (%)		Disease reaction ^a			
							Wet season	Dry season	Wet season		Dry season	
									BB	ShB	ShR	BI ^b
V20A	V20	89	75	10	Fair	100	2	21	5	7	5	2
V41A	V41	95	80	9	Poor	100	6	18	3	7	5	3
Zhen Shan 97A	Zhen Shan 97	93	78	9	Poor	100	2	26	5	7	3	5
Yar ai zhao A	Yar ai zhao	97	77	8	Poor	95	9	27	5	7	5	5
MS519A	IR24	120	95	12	Fair	85	9	17	3	5	3	4
IR46829A	IR19792-15-2-2	95	75	14	Fair	97	9	13	5	7	5	3
IR46830A	IR19807-21-2-2	102	76	16	Fair	100	7	30	5	5	5	—
IR46831A	Jikkoku Surranai 52-37	110	85	18	Fair	92	8	20	3	5	3	6
IR48483A	MS365	110	80	18	Fair	100	6	28	3	5	3	8
IR21845-90-3A (IR54752A)	IR21845-90-3 (IR54752B)	140	110	12	Fair	95	10	19	5	5	3	—
	CV (%)		12.6	15.7								
	LSD (0.05)		14	3								

^a Field evaluation. ^b Evaluated in 1986 blast nursery according to IRRI Standard evaluation system for rice scale.

terms of plant type and reactions to diseases, especially to sheath blight (ShB) (see table). But they showed higher spikelet sterility.

IRRI improved lines IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR21845-90-3A (IR54752A) had acceptable phenotype

with heavy tillering. They were resistant to blast (BI) but moderately susceptible to bacterial blight (BB) and sheath rot (ShR) in the field.

Seed setting in A lines was lower in the wet season than in the dry season.

In general, IRRI improved A lines

showed better adaptability to local conditions than the A lines from China. However, V20A, IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR54752A grew reasonably well and could be used to develop rice hybrids in Vietnam. □

Susceptibility of A lines and B lines to bacterial blight (BB)

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Fifteen isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* were used to

inoculate male sterile (A) lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A, and their corresponding maintainer (B) lines during the first growing season of 1985. The test was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plants were inoculated at booting with a bacterial suspension of about 10⁹

cells/ml, using the clipping technique. Length of lesion was measured 3 wk after inoculation on a sample of 20 leaves/plot.

Cytoplasm affected the expression of BB reaction significantly and interaction between nucleus and cytoplasm was detected (see table). A lines were less susceptible than the B lines. □

Susceptibility of A and B lines to BB. ^a Fuzhou, China, 1985.

Isolate group	Isolate no.	Lesion length (cm)					
		Zhen Shan 97			V20		
		A	B	A-B ^a	A	B	A-B
III	83476-2	26.9	29.4	-2.5*	26.5	28.8	-2.3*
IV	79113-4	27.1	28.5	-1.4	25.8	26.1	-0.9
III	83500-1	26.0	28.2	-2.2**	28.7	27.8	1.0
IV	83505-1	25.6	28.1	-2.5*	26.6	27.3	-0.7
III	82409-3	25.1	27.0	-1.9**	21.2	24.0	-2.8*
III	83498-1	23.1	26.8	-3.7*	22.9	25.0	-2.1**
IV	82443-1	22.8	26.2	-3.4*	24.6	25.1	-0.5
III	82400-1	23.5	27.3	-3.8*	21.6	23.1	-1.5
IV	80153-1	25.3	26.5	-1.2	23.1	22.9	0.2
III	83470-2	23.0	24.4	-1.4	20.8	21.7	-0.9
II	81267-1	23.5	27.1	-3.6*	21.0	22.9	-1.9**
III	83485-3	23.4	23.4	0.0	23.8	22.6	1.2
III	79048-1	21.5	24.7	-3.2*	16.1	17.9	-1.8**
I	81259-7	9.0	9.7	-0.7	9.9	10.7	-0.8
I	81317-3	7.3	8.1	-0.8	7.5	7.6	-0.1

^a Significance at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels.

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